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Additional Information

In-Silico Classifiers for the Assessment of Drug Proarrhythmicity

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ABSTRACT

Drug-induced torsade de pointes (TdP) is a life-threatening ventricular arrhythmia responsible for the withdrawal of many drugs from the market. Currently used TdP-risk assessment methods are effective but also expensive and prone to produce false positives. In recent years, *in-silico* cardiac simulations have proven to be a valuable tool for the prediction of drug effects. The objective of this work is to evaluate different biomarkers of drug-induced proarrhythmic risk and to develop an *in-silico* risk classifier.

Cellular simulations were performed using a modified version of the O'Hara et al. ventricular action potential model and existing pharmacological data (IC₅₀ and Effective Free Therapeutic Plasma Concentration, EFTPC) for 109 drugs of known torsadogenic risk (51 positive). For each compound, 4 biomarkers were tested: T_x (drug concentration leading to a 10% prolongation of the action potential over the EFTPC), T_{qNet} (net charge carried by ionic currents when exposed to 10

18 times the EFTPC with respect to the net charge in control), T_{triang} (triangulation for a drug
19 concentration of 10 times the EFTPC over triangulation in control) and T_{EAD} (drug concentration
20 originating early afterdepolarizations over EFTPC). ROC-curves were built for each biomarker to
21 evaluate their individual predictive quality. At the optimal cut-off point, accuracies for T_x , $T_{q\text{Net}}$,
22 T_{triang} , and T_{EAD} were 89.9%, 91.7%, 90.8%, and 78.9% respectively. The resulting accuracy of
23 the hERG IC_{50} test (current biomarker) was 78.9%. When combining T_x , $T_{q\text{Net}}$ and T_{triang} into a
24 classifier based on decision trees, the prediction improves, achieving an accuracy of 94.5%. The
25 sensitivity analysis revealed that most of the effects on the action potential are mainly due to
26 changes in I_{K_r} , I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} and I_{K_s} . In fact, considering that drugs affect only these 4 currents, TdP-
27 risk classification can be as accurate as when considering effects on the 7 main currents proposed
28 by the CiPA initiative. Finally, we built a ready-to-use tool (based on more than 450,000
29 simulations) which can be used to quickly assess the proarrhythmic risk of a compound. In
30 conclusion, our *in-silico* tool can be useful for preclinical assessment of TdP-risk and to reduce
31 costs related with new drug development. The TdP-risk assessment tool and the software used in
32 this work are available at: <https://riunet.upv.es/handle/10251/136919>.

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38 1. INTRODUCTION

39 Drug-induced torsade de pointes (TdP) is a life-threatening arrhythmia characterized by a
40 gradual change in the amplitude and twisting of the QRS complexes.¹ It is one of the most feared
41 adverse drug reactions. In fact, several compounds, without heart-related therapeutic indications,
42 have been withdrawn from the market due to its ability to induce TdP.² Thus, the evaluation of
43 proarrhythmic risk is considered an important public health problem and is receiving attention
44 from governments, regulatory authorities, and pharmacological companies because of its socio-
45 economic consequences.

46 In the 1990s it was recognized that the induction of TdP was highly correlated with
47 pharmacological blockade of the human ether-à-go-go-related gene (hERG) channel (which
48 mediates the rapid component of delayed rectifier current $-I_{Kr}$) and a prolongation of the QT
49 interval.³ As a consequence, two regulatory guidelines (S7B -non clinical guidance- and E14 -
50 clinical guidance) were established by the International Council on Harmonization (ICH) for
51 cardiac risk assessment. These protocols have been successful in preventing torsadogenic drugs
52 being commercialized.⁴ However, by focusing exclusively on hERG blockade and QT
53 prolongation, they have also contributed to discard from the development pipeline a large number
54 of potentially useful compound. Indeed, many studies^{5,6} have shown that there are drugs, such as
55 verapamil, that produce a hERG block but do not lead to TdP. Other ion currents have also been
56 shown to influence the appearance of TdP. Therefore, a more accurate method for the torsadogenic
57 risk assessment at early stages of drug development, which takes into account multichannel
58 interactions, would be of paramount importance for safety pharmacology.

59 In the last years, biophysical models and computational simulations are being widely used to
60 improve the prediction of drug cardiotoxicity. New international paradigms for the proarrhythmic
61 assessment of drugs, such as the Comprehensive *in-vitro* Proarrhythmia Assay (CiPA), consider
62 that *in-silico* simulations of proarrhythmic effects for different compounds have a key role to link
63 data from *in-vitro* assays to changes in cell behavior and are essential to improve
64 arrhythmogenicity prediction.^{4,7} Numerous *in-silico* classifications tools have been published⁸⁻¹⁴,
65 which have shown to improve TdP-risk assessment and are becoming gradually an alternative to
66 reduce animal experiments during early stages of drug development. These *in-silico* evaluations
67 are based on performing different simulations (reported studies use single-cell models, one-
68 dimensional models or even whole-heart simulations) to calculate a set of features such as action
69 potential duration, diastolic calcium or transmural dispersion of repolarization, among others, and
70 use them for TdP risk discrimination. These strategies have demonstrated the capability to make
71 good predictions^{8,15-17}, however, there is still space for improvement, since they still present some
72 limitations, such as: a reduced number of compounds, considering drug effects on just a small
73 number of ion channels, and usage of non-updated biophysical models, among others. Hence, the
74 development of new TdP risk assessment methods based on *in-silico* simulations can be of high
75 interest.

76 In a previous work, our group developed a method for the early screening of drug-induced
77 proarrhythmic risk. It consists of 4 matrices that taking into account blocking effects on I_{Kr} , I_{CaL}
78 and I_{Ks} provide the value of an arrhythmogenic index called T_x predicting if the drug is
79 proarrhythmic or not.¹⁰ It was successfully tested in 84 compounds, at that time, one of the largest
80 drug databases employed. The method was implemented in the QT/TdP Risk Screen tool available
81 on the web based InSilicoTrials.com platform (www.insilicotrials.com) built on the Microsoft

82 Azure cloud environment, in compliance with the highest standards of security and privacy. The
83 aims of this study are: (i) to improve our *in-silico* classifier for the assessment of TdP risk by taking
84 into account the 7 ionic currents selected by CiPA initiative due to their important role in
85 arrhythmogenesis (I_{Na} , I_{NaL} , I_{Kr} , I_{to} , I_{CaL} , I_{K1} , and I_{Ks}), increasing our database, defining new
86 effective biomarkers, and using different machine learning tools to achieve a more reliable and
87 robust prediction, (ii) to identify the ionic currents that have the most significant impact on TdP
88 risk prediction. This will help to reduce the amount of in vitro experiments necessary to
89 characterize a drug and simulate its effect, thus accelerating the process of drug development and
90 reducing the associated costs.

91 2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

92 2.1. Cellular *in-silico* simulations

93 The electrophysiological characteristics of human ventricular cells were simulated using a
94 modified version of the human endocardial ventricular action potential (AP) model published by
95 O'Hara et al.¹⁸ The O'Hara et al. model is one of the most recent and used *in-silico* AP model.^{19,20}
96 In fact, it was proposed by the CiPA initiative as the starting point for the development on *in-silico*
97 tools for regulatory decision making.⁴ However, the O'Hara et al. model¹⁸ still has some issues
98 that should be addressed.²¹ In this work, the model modifications include a modulation of 5 channel
99 conductances according to Dutta et al.²² and a reformulation of the activation and inactivation gates
100 of I_{Na} , plus a reduction of its conductance by 60%^{20,23}. The modification in channel conductances
101 was carried out aiming at better reproducing experimental data of drug effects. As suggested by
102 Dutta et al.²², the following conductances were scaled: I_{Kr} by 1.119, I_{Ks} by 1.648, I_{K1} by 1.414, I_{CaL}

103 by 1.018, and I_{NaL} by 2.274. For further details about the equations describing I_{Na} dynamics see
104 **Table S1** in the **Supplementary Material**.

105 Drug effects on the AP were simulated via the simple pore block model, as in previous
106 works^{9,10,16,24}. Thus, the block produced on each current was simulated by scaling the channel's
107 maximal conductance (g_i). This scaling factor was calculated using the standard Hill equation (**eq.**
108 **1**). In this work we considered drug effects on the 7 ionic currents selected by the Ion Channel
109 Working Group of the CiPA initiative for playing the most important role in the generation of the
110 AP and cardiac arrhythmias (I_{Na} , I_{NaL} , I_{Kr} , I_{to} , I_{CaL} , I_{K1} , and I_{Ks}).^{4,7}

$$g_{i,drug} = g_i \left[1 + \left(\frac{D}{IC_{50,i}} \right)^h \right]^{-1} \quad (1)$$

111 where $g_{i,drug}$ is the maximal conductance of channel i in the presence of the drug, D is the drug
112 concentration, $IC_{50,i}$ is the half-maximal response dose for that drug and current through channel
113 i and h is the Hill coefficient indicating the number of molecules of drug that are assumed to be
114 sufficient to block one ion channel.

115 All simulations were carried out with a basic cycle length (BCL) of 1000 ms and a stimulus of
116 1.5-fold the diastolic threshold of amplitude and a duration of 0.5 ms. Measurements of indices
117 and biomarkers were done once achieved the steady-state (after 1,000 beats starting from control
118 -no drug- steady-state initial values).

119 2.2. Drugs data set

120 In this work, we assessed the proarrhythmic risk of 109 drugs using derived-features (parameters
121 obtained from biophysical models and explained in detail in the following subsection). For these

122 compounds, the ground truth was taken from CredibleMeds²⁵. CredibleMeds classification is based
123 on an extensive search of both the literature and public databases, which is continuously updated
124 in-light of new evidence and is recognized by the clinical community.

125 This database defines 4 drug-induced TdP risk categories: class 1, compounds that prolong QT
126 interval and are clearly associated with a known risk of TdP, even when taken as recommended;
127 class 2, compounds with possible risk of TdP; class 3, drugs associated with TdP but only under
128 certain conditions (excessive dose, interactions, patients with pathological conditions, etc.); class
129 4, drugs with lack of evidence to be placed in any of the other classes. The classification of the
130 109 drugs studied in this work is provided in **Table 1**. In this work, for the purpose of developing
131 binary classifiers, we grouped together class 1 and 2 as TdP+ and 3 and 4 as TdP-.

132 Ajmaline, Tedisamil and Azimilide are not included in the CredibleMeds classification, but they
133 were included in class 1 according to Mirams et al.¹⁶, Romero et al.¹⁰, and Fermini et al.⁷. Other
134 drugs (marked with an asterisk in **Table 1**) that are not included in CredibleMeds and lack of
135 evidence of TdP were considered as class 4 (as in Romero et al.¹⁰).

136 **Table 1.** TdP-risk classification of the 109 drugs used in this study. Each drug is color-coded
137 according to its torsadogenic risk: red for class 1 (known risk of TdP), orange for class 2 (possible
138 risk of TdP), yellow for class 3 (conditional risk of TdP), green for class 4 (drugs with lack of
139 evidence of TdP). An asterisk indicates that the drug was not in CredibleMeds list and was assigned
140 to a class according to the literature.

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Compound Name	Class	Compound Name	Class	Compound Name	Class
Ajmaline	1*	Pimozide	1	Deferasirox	4*
Amiodarone	1	Clozapine	2	Desvenlafaxine	4
Astemizole	1	Desipramine	2	Diazepam	4
Azithromycin	1	Dolasetron	2	Diltiazem	4
Bepidil	1	Lapatinib	2	Doxorubicin	4
Chloroquine	1	Lopinavir	2	Duloxetine	4
Chlorpromazine	1	Nilotinib	2	Ebastine	4*
Cilostazol	1	Paliperidone	2	Eltrombopag	4
Cisapride	1	Risperidone	2	Etravirine	4*
Clarithromycin	1	Ritonavir	2	Everolimus	4
Disopyramide	1	Saquinavir	2	Lamivudine	4
Dofetilide	1	Sertindole	2	Lidocaine	4
Domperidone	1	Sunitinib	2	Linezolid	4
Donepezil	1	Tolterodine	2	Loratadine	4
Dronedarone	1	Tamoxifen	2	Maraviroc	4*
Droperidol	1	Amitriptyline	3	Metoprolol	4
Erythromycin	1	Diphenhydramine	3	Mexiletine	4
Flecainide	1	Famotidine	3	Mibefradil	4*
Gatifloxacin	1	Fluvoxamine	3	Mitoxantrone	4
Halofantrine	1	Metronidazole	3	Nebivolol	4
Haloperidol	1	Nelfinavir	3	Nifedipine	4
Ibutilide	1	Paroxetine	3	Nitrendipine	4*
Levofloxacin	1	Propafenone	3	Nisoldipine	4*
Methadone	1	Quetiapine	3	Oxybutynin	4
Moxifloxacin	1	Quinine	3	Palonosetron	4
Ondansetron	1	Ranolazine	3	Pentobarbital	4*
Procainamide	1	Solifenacin	3	Phenytoin	4
Quinidine	1	Voriconazole	3	Propranolol	4
Sotalol	1	Alvimopan	4*	Raltegravir	4
Sparfloxacin	1	Ambrisentan	4	Ribavirin	4
Tedisamil	1*	Aspirin	4	Rufinamide	4*
Terfenadine	1	Ceftriaxone	4	Sildenafil	4
Terodiline	1	Chlorpheniramine	4	Silodosin	4
Thioridazine	1	Cibenzoline	4*	Sitagliptin	4*
Azimidazole	1*	Darifenacin	4	Tadalafil	4
Vandetanib	1	Darunavir	4	Telbivudine	4*
				Verapamil	4

144 For each of these 109 drugs, IC₅₀ values and Hill coefficients (h) for I_{Na}, I_{NaL}, I_{Kr}, I_{to}, I_{CaL}, I_{K1},
145 and I_{Ks}, and human effective free therapeutic plasma concentration (EFTPC) were obtained from
146 either public databases, like DrugBank, DailyMed or PubChem, or from the scientific literature,

147 avoiding always data extracted from *Xenopus oocytes*. EFTPC values were used directly from the
148 source (when available) or calculated taking into account the protein-bound fraction and the peak
149 plasma concentrations (see Supplementary Material, Table S2). When multiple IC_{50} were
150 presented, we considered that all published data represented a distribution of values affected by
151 random error. To deal with that variability and summarize this distribution in a robust value, the
152 value at the center of the distribution was selected (i.e., the median value). For the Hill coefficient,
153 we took the one associated with the median IC_{50} value chosen. In those cases when no IC_{50} value
154 was found, the block of the corresponding channel was not considered in our simulations. When
155 several EFTPC values were found, we considered the worst-case scenario by selecting the value
156 for the highest dose. The EFTPC, IC_{50} , and Hill coefficient values for the 109 drugs are listed in
157 the **Supplementary Material, Table S2**.

158 2.3. Torsadogenic indices

159 In recent years, various “derived-features” have been proposed for the assessment of drug
160 proarrhythmicity. “Derived-features” are parameters or indices obtained from biophysical
161 computational models and have proven to be promising metrics to provide mechanism-based
162 classification of compounds. Furthermore, they have the potential to lead to a replacement of
163 animal experiments in the early phases of drug development.²⁶ In Parikh and colleagues^{24,26} a brief
164 review of the *in-silico* arrhythmogenic biomarkers proposed the last years can be consulted.

165 In this work, we have studied four different torsadogenic indices (see **Figure 1**):

- 166 • T_x : this arrhythmogenic index was proposed by Romero et al.¹⁰ and tested in 84 drugs,
167 providing a classification accuracy of 88%. It is defined as the ratio between the
168 concentration of drug that provokes a 10% prolongation of action potential duration at 90%

169 repolarization (APD₉₀) in control conditions and the EFTPC. Therefore, a high T_x value
170 means that the concentration needed to increase APD₉₀ a 10% is much higher than the
171 EFTPC, and thus the drug is safe. In **Figure 1 (A)**, AP in control conditions (black line)
172 and AP with a 10% APD₉₀ prolongation due to drug effects are shown. It can be seen that
173 safe drugs (such as loratadine -plotted in green) have a greater T_x value than proarrhythmic
174 drugs (such as ibutilide -plotted in red) because their effect on APD prolongation is weak
175 and the concentration needed to prolong APD₉₀ a 10% is much higher.

$$T_x = \frac{[D]_{APD\uparrow 10\%}}{EFTPC} \quad (2)$$

176 • **T_{qNet}**: this index is based on the concept of qNet (net charge) that was proposed in Dutta et
177 al.¹⁵ qNet is calculated as the area under the curve traced by the net current
178 ($I_{net}=I_{CaL}+I_{NaL}+I_{Kr}+I_{Ks}+I_{K1}+I_{to}$) during a whole beat. This index was able to separate with
179 accuracy the 12 training CiPA drugs into the desired target groups. In addition, Li et al.⁵
180 used the qNet value averaged across 1-4 x C_{max} and successfully predicted the TdP risk of
181 on 16 test compounds.⁵ Here, we define T_{qNet} as the ratio between the net charge carried
182 by I_{net} when exposed to 10 times the EFTPC with respect to the net charge in control
183 conditions (**eq. 3**). For a given drug, a T_{qNet} near 1 means that the net charge at 10 times
184 the EFTPC is very similar to the net charge at control conditions. Values higher than 1
185 indicate an increase in repolarization reserve, and therefore safety²⁷; on the contrary, low
186 values of T_{qNet} are associated to a higher propensity of TdP. In **Figure 1 (B)**, the net current
187 for the last beat under 10 times the EFTPC concentration of loratadine (low risk drug) is
188 plotted in green and the net current under 10xEFTPC concentration of ibutilide (high risk
189 drug), in red. It can be observed that torsadogenic drugs have less net charge with respect

190 to control condition and consequently smaller T_{qNet} . 10 times the EFTPC concentration was
191 chosen to distinguish drug effects without being an excessively high dose.

$$T_{qNet} = \frac{qNet_{at\ 10\cdot EFTPC}}{qNet_{control}} \quad (3)$$

192 • **T_{triang}**: this index is the ratio between triangulation (APD_{90} - APD_{30}) for a drug concentration
193 of 10xEFTPC over triangulation in control (**eq. 4**). Similar to T_{qNet} , values near 1 mean that
194 the triangulation at 10xEFTPC is practically equal to triangulation at control conditions.
195 However, in this case, as torsadogenic drugs produce more changes in the morphology of
196 AP and prolong its duration, its T_{triang} is expected to be greater than 1. Specifically, higher
197 T_{triang} , means that the drug affects more in the repolarization phase, originating lower
198 repolarization reserve, which is related with the development of TdP²⁷. In **Figure 1 (C)**
199 changes on AP at 10xEFTPC of loratadine and ibutilide are represented. Ibutilide has a
200 greater impact on the AP, producing a longer triangulation, while loratadine effects on AP
201 at that concentration is negligible, being equal to AP control.

$$T_{triang} = \frac{(APD_{90} - APD_{30})_{at\ 10\cdot EFTPC}}{(APD_{90} - APD_{30})_{control}} \quad (4)$$

202 • **T_{EAD}**: this index measures the likelihood to develop an early after-depolarization (EAD),
203 which is thought to be a key determinant for TdP development²⁸. It is defined as the ratio
204 between the drug concentration needed to originate an EAD or a repolarization failure over
205 the EFTPC (**eq. 5**). Thus, the lower the T_{EAD} , the higher ability of the drug to induce EADs
206 or repolarization failure and the more dangerous the drug. An EAD was defined as any
207 event with a positive voltage gradient ($dV/dt > 0ms$) after 100 ms from the beginning of
208 the AP. It was considered that there was a repolarization failure when membrane voltage
209 at the end of the beat was higher than resting membrane voltage ($V_m > -40$ mV). The

210 stimulation protocol for the generation of EADs and repolarization failure was similar to
211 that used by Viswanathan and Rudy²⁹: for a given drug concentration, 999 stimuli at a 1
212 Hz BCL were simulated, then a 2000 ms pause was left and an extra stimulus was applied.
213 The drug concentration was gradually increased from EFTPC until an EAD appeared or
214 until 10^5 times the EFTPC. If no EAD appeared at this concentration the T_{EAD} was
215 considered 10^5 . Traces of AP at drug concentration producing EADs are shown in **Figure**
216 **1 (D)**. An EAD can be observed when ibutilide is applied at 20 times the EFTPC (red line),
217 while in the case of loratadine (green line), even at 10^5 times the EFTPC there is no EAD
218 (although it increases APD with respect control -black line).

$$T_{EAD} = \frac{[D]_{EADs}}{EFTPC} \quad (5)$$

219 All indices were analyzed for the last beat in simulations of 1000 beats.

220

221 **Figure 1.** Studied arrhythmogenic indices. Curves corresponding to simulations in control

222 conditions are represented in black; red curves represent AP under effects of a high proarrhythmic

223 risk drug (ibutilide), while green ones represent effects under a low proarrhythmic risk drug

224 (loratadine). (A) T_x index. The AP under drug effects with an APD_{90} 10% longer than the control

225 APD_{90} is represented. Traces for low and high risk drugs are overlapped, but the concentration

226 needed to achieve a 10% APD_{90} prolongation is much higher in the case of the low risk drug and

227 thus T_x is much greater. (B) Charge carried by I_{net} . The area under the I_{net} curve for the last beat

228 when the low risk drug is applied at a concentration of $10 \cdot \text{EFTPC}$ is plotted in green. The area
229 under the I_{Net} curve for the high risk one is plotted in red. (C) T_{triang} index. APs under $10 \cdot \text{EFTPC}$
230 are traced for a torsadogenic drug and for a non-torsadogenic drug. Ibutilide (high risk) has greater
231 impact on the AP, producing a longer triangulation. Loratadine (low risk) and control curves are
232 coincident because the effect of loratadine at those concentrations on the AP is negligible. (D)
233 T_{EAD} index. APs curves at the dose generating EAD are represented. When the high risk drug is
234 applied at $20 \cdot \text{EFTPC}$, it provokes an EAD (positive voltage gradient during the repolarization
235 phase). For the low risk drug, there is no EAD even at $10^5 \cdot \text{EFTPC}$.

236 2.4. Sensitivity analysis

237 One of the objectives of this work is to determine the currents which have more influence on the
238 prediction of cardiotoxicity. In this sense, we performed a sensitivity analysis following a similar
239 methodology to that proposed by Britton et al.³⁰ Briefly, first we generated a population of 1,000
240 virtual drugs. We considered the virtual drugs affecting the 7 most arrhythmogenic currents
241 according to the CiPA initiative (I_{Na} , I_{NaL} , I_{Kr} , I_{to} , I_{CaL} , I_{K1} , and I_{Ks}). Thus, a virtual drug consists
242 of a set of 7 scale factors (one for each ionic current) between $\pm 60\%$. This range includes the vast
243 majority of inhibition or enhancement effects that drugs usually have at therapeutic concentrations.
244 The parameter sets of scaling factors were obtained using latin hypercube sampling (LHS). After
245 running simulations with the virtual drugs, the biomarkers were computed, and the partial
246 correlation coefficients (PCC) method was applied, relating the indices with the currents. As they
247 are virtual drugs and their EFTPC are not known, the biomarkers calculated were surrogates of the
248 4 indices proposed. They were APD_{90} (surrogate of T_x), $T_{q\text{Net_mod}}$ ($q\text{Net}$ at the effect of the virtual
249 drug over $q\text{Net}$ control – as EFTPC was not known) and $T_{\text{triang_mod}}$ (triangulation at the effect of
250 the virtual drug over triangulation control).

251 We also tested other two methodologies to perform the sensitivity analysis. After obtaining a
252 population of virtual drugs using a log-normal distribution of scaling factors between $\pm 60\%$, the
253 simulations were run and the biomarkers computed. In one case, partial least square (PLS)
254 regression using the NIPALS algorithm³¹ was applied and, in the other, a multiple linear
255 regression³² was performed.

256 Based on the results of this analysis, the proarrhythmic indices were recalculated taking into
257 account only the currents with greater impact. These biomarkers were used to build new torsadogenic
258 drug classifiers to study how the proarrhythmic prediction changed.

259 2.5. Torsadogenic drug classifier

260 Finally, we combined T_x , T_{qNet} , and T_{triang} indices into a unique classifier to analyze whether the
261 classification performance improves. The *in-silico* TdP-risk classifier was built using MATLAB
262 (Mathworks Inc. Natwick, MA, USA). First, a 9-fold cross validation was applied. The original
263 dataset (109 compounds) was randomly split in 9 sets and in each iteration, one of the sets (12
264 compounds) was left out as test series while the remaining 9 sets (97 compounds) were used as
265 training series. A classification decision tree was built using the training set in each iteration, thus
266 obtaining 9 classification trees. For each decision tree, the maximum number of splits allowed was
267 4. To obtain the output of the binary risk classifier, a majority voting technique³³ between the
268 prediction of each decision tree was applied.

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272 3. RESULTS

273 3.1. Predictive performance of the arrhythmogenic indices

274 The value of each arrhythmogenic index for the 109 drugs studied in this work was calculated.
275 The ROC-curves of the indices T_x (black), T_{qNet} (red) and T_{triang} (blue) are shown in **Figure 2 (A)**.
276 This figure also depicts the ROC-curve for two metrics based on results from the hERG assay,
277 which is currently used as a surrogate marker of TdP risk according to ICH S7B guidelines. These
278 two metrics are: pIC_{50} hERG ($-\log IC_{50}$ hERG) and hERG $IC_{50}/EFTPC$. It can be observed that the
279 ROC-curves for T_x , T_{qNet} , and T_{triang} are similar, being the area under the curve (AUC) 0.94, 0.94,
280 and 0.93, respectively. All of them are greater than the AUC for the metrics based on IC_{50} hERG,
281 which are 0.90 for IC_{50} hERG/EFTPC and 0.82 for pIC_{50} hERG test.

282 **Figure 2 (B)** shows the confusion matrices for T_x , T_{qNet} , T_{triang} , and IC_{50} hERG/EFTPC indices
283 at the optimal cut-points, which is the threshold that achieves the nearest point to the upper-left
284 corner of the ROC-curve, where sensitivity and specificity are maximal. The optimal cut-points
285 were: 8 for T_x , 1.19 for T_{triang} , 0.88 for T_{qNet} , and 39 for IC_{50} hERG/EFTPC. It can be highlighted
286 that T_x , T_{qNet} , and T_{triang} tests led to very similar accuracies (around 90%), again higher than the
287 performance of the pIC_{50} hERG and IC_{50} hERG/EFTPC tests. At the optimal cut-point for T_x test,
288 48 out of the 51 (94% specificity) the torsadogenic drugs (class 1 and class 2 – see **Table 1**) and
289 50 of the 58 (86% sensitivity) non-torsadogenic drugs (class 3 and 4) were correctly classified.
290 The performance for the decision $T_{qNet} < 0.88$ was: specificity (true negative rate) of 93% and
291 sensitivity (true positive rate) of 90%, leading to an accuracy of 91.7%. The T_{triang} test classified
292 correctly 48 proarrhythmic compound and 51 non-proarrhythmic, which corresponds to a
293 sensitivity of 94% and a specificity of 88%. Regarding the metrics based on IC_{50} hERG, the

294 accuracy obtained with the threshold IC_{50} hERG/EFTPC < 39 was 87.2%, classifying correctly 48
 295 proarrhythmic compounds and 47 non-proarrhythmic compounds. For the test pIC_{50} hERG (not
 296 shown in the figure), at the optimal cut-point (pIC_{50} hERG > 5.8) the resulting accuracy yielded
 297 78.9%. With this test 18 TdP+ drugs were considered as non-torsadogenic (65% of sensitivity) and
 298 5 TdP- as torsadogenic (91% of specificity).

299
 300 **Figure 2.** (A) ROC curves for T_x (black), T_{qNet} (red), T_{triang} (blue), pIC_{50} hERG (green) and IC_{50}
 301 hERG/EFTPC (orange). The dashed line indicates the performance of a model that does not
 302 discriminate. (B) Confusion matrices for the arrhythmogenic indices at the optimal cutoff point

303 (where sensitivity and specificity are maximal). Columns (TdP+ and TdP-) indicate the actual
304 classification of the compounds (Table 1), rows (+ and -) indicate the prediction made by the index
305 studied. The cutoff points are: 8 for T_x , 1.19 for T_{triang} , 0.88 for T_{qNet} and 39 for IC_{50} hERG/EFTPC.
306 True positives rates (TPR), true negatives rates (TNR) and accuracies (Acc) are also shown.

307 Note that results for T_{EAD} were not included in this figure for the sake of clarity, as it was the
308 index that performed worst. Its performance was slightly lower than the pIC_{50} hERG, obtaining an
309 AUC of 0.80 and an accuracy at the optimal cut-off point of 78.9%. The resulting sensitivity was
310 73% (14 false positive drugs) and the specificity 85% (9 false negative).

311
 312 **Figure 3.** TdP-risk classification of the 109 compounds with different proarrhythmic indices at the
 313 optimal cutoff point. The criteria was that drugs with $hERG\ IC_{50}/EFTPC < 39$, $T_x < 8$, $T_{qNet} <$
 314 0.88 and $T_{triang} > 1.19$ were predicted as torsadogenic. Class 1 and 2 compounds are considered as
 315 unsafe drugs, while class 3 and 4 as safe drugs.

316 **Figure 3** shows the value of the indices IC_{50} hERG/EFTPC, T_x , T_{qNet} , and T_{triang} for the 109
317 drugs and the torsadogenic risk classification of this compounds using 4 different criteria to
318 consider a drug as torsadogenic: IC_{50} hERG/EFTPC < 39, T_x < 8, T_{qNet} < 0.88, and T_{triang} > 119.
319 According to IC_{50} hERG/EFTPC test, cilostazol and donepezil, which are class 1 compounds
320 (compounds with known risk of TdP), and tamoxifen (class 2 compound) were predicted as safe
321 drugs. For safe drugs, the IC_{50} hERG/EFTPC test misclassified five class 3 drugs (propafenone,
322 ranolazine, quinine, metronidazole and fluvoxamine) and six class 4 drugs (verapamil, mexiletine,
323 cibenzoline, linezolid, ceftriaxone and phenytoin). It is worth noting that T_x , T_{qNet} , and T_{triang} index
324 misclassified as nontorsadogenic (false negative) the same two class 1 compounds, namely
325 cilostazol and donepezil, as well as tamoxifen, a class 2 compound (compounds with possible risk
326 of TdP). They also misclassified as torsadogenic the same two class 3 compounds (fluvoxamine
327 and propafenone) and the same class 4 compound (cibenzoline). In addition, T_x and T_{triang} both
328 misclassified class 3 compounds: metronidazole, quinine, and ranolazine, and the class 4 compound
329 verapamil. T_x and T_{qNet} missclassified doxorubicin, a class 4 drug. T_{qNet} also misclassified as non
330 torsadogenic class 2 drugs: ritonavir and saquinavir.

331 3.2. Sensitivity analysis

332 Next, we wanted to analyze which of the 7 CiPA currents have more effect on the
333 electrophysiological characteristics of the action potential. We simulated the effect of a population
334 of 1,000 virtual drugs and applied the partial correlation coefficients (PCC) method, as described
335 in the Methods section to estimate the association between the arrhythmogenic indices and the 7
336 currents. The effects of these virtual drugs on the action potential and on the intracellular calcium
337 transient are shown in **Figure 4 (A and B)**. Control APs and calcium transient are plotted in a
338 thick black line. It can be observed that some drugs shorten the AP while others prolong it. For the

339 intracellular calcium dynamics it can also be observed that some drugs increase the amplitude of
 340 the calcium transient while others decrease it. Thus, with this population of virtual drugs we can
 341 represent a wide variety of pharmacological effects.

342
 343 **Figure 4.** Results of sensitivity analysis. (A) Effects of the 1,000 virtual drugs on the action
 344 potential. Black line represents control AP. (B) Effects of the 1,000 virtual drugs on intracellular
 345 calcium dynamics. Black trace corresponds to control calcium transient. (C) PCCs values of each
 346 of the 7 CiPA drugs for APD₉₀ (blue), T_{triang_mod} (red) and T_{qNet_mod} (green).

347 The PCC for each current and biomarker are plotted in **Figure 4 (C)**. For APD₉₀, the currents
348 that have a higher PCC value are: I_{Kr} (-0.97), I_{NaL} (0.74), I_{CaL} (0.60), and I_{Ks} (-0.54). I_{K1} coefficient
349 is -0.47, and the other coefficients are lower than 0.14. For T_{triang_mod} index the currents with more
350 influence are: I_{Kr} (-0.96), I_{K1} (0.63), I_{NaL} (0.56), and I_{CaL} (-0.35). In this case, the PCC value for I_{Ks}
351 is -0.25, for I_{Na} is -0.18 and for I_{to}, -0.11. For T_{qNet_mod} the higher PCC values are for I_{Kr} (0.98),
352 I_{NaL} (-0.98), I_{CaL} (-0.91), and I_{Na} (0.89). The other values are below 0.62, which is I_{Ks} coefficient.
353 It should be noted that the effects of I_{to} on the 3 biomarkers are practically negligible. If we add
354 the 3 coefficients of each current in absolute value to represent the global relevance of each current
355 on the value of the biomarkers, the currents yielding the highest values are I_{Kr} (2.91), I_{NaL} (2.27),
356 I_{CaL}(1.85), and I_{Ks} (1.41). Thus, these results suggest that the currents that are globally more
357 relevant to predict the torsadogenic effects of a drug are I_{Kr}, I_{CaL}, I_{NaL}, and I_{Ks}. It is true that the
358 coefficient of I_{Na} for T_{qNet_mod} is higher than the I_{Ks} PCC coefficient, but for the other biomarkers,
359 the influence of I_{Na} is smaller than the influence of I_{Ks}. For T_{triang_mod} the I_{K1} PCC coefficient is also
360 higher than I_{Ks} PCC coefficient, but again, for the other biomarkers, I_{Ks} is more relevant.

361 In the **Supplementary Material**, the results of the sensitivity analysis using a multivariable
362 linear regression (**Figure S1**) and the PLS method (**Figure S2**) are shown. Both methods obtain
363 very similar coefficient values. It can be observed that the sign of the biomarker-ion current
364 dependency (positive or negative) is the same with both sensitivity methods. In addition, the
365 currents that have a greater influence (greater value of the addition 3 absolute values of the
366 coefficients) are the same: I_{Kr}, I_{NaL}, I_{CaL}, and I_{Ks}. Therefore, according to our results, it can be
367 deduced that regardless of the method used, qualitatively the same results are obtained. That is,
368 the currents with the most significant global influence on TdP-risk prediction biomarkers are I_{Kr},
369 I_{CaL}, I_{NaL}, and I_{Ks}.

370 3.3. Binary torsadogenic risk classifiers

371 To improve the power of prediction we combined T_x , T_{qNet} , and T_{triang} into a unique classifier.
372 As described in Section 2.5, using the 3 proarrhythmic indices as inputs, we built 9 decision
373 trees. Each decision tree consisted of a maximum of 4 cut-off points. The cut-off points were
374 calculated specifically for each decision tree aiming to achieve optimal performance. 2 of the 9
375 decision trees that constitute this classifier are represented in **Figure 5**. The remaining decision
376 trees are shown in **Figure S3**. For each drug, each tree takes several decisions and makes a
377 prediction. For example, in tree 1 (**Figure 5**), T_{qNet} index is evaluated first. If it is less than 0.91,
378 then the next step is to evaluate T_{triang} . Depending on whether T_{triang} is greater or smaller than 1.009,
379 the tree predicts that the drug is safe or torsadogenic. On the contrary, if the drug has a T_{qNet} greater
380 than 0.91 the other branch of the tree should be followed. Thus, after evaluating T_{qNet} , T_x is studied.
381 If it is greater than 14.2, then the drug is safe. If not, T_{triang} has to be finally evaluated to decide if
382 the drug will be safe or dangerous. The rest of the trees make a prediction in a similar way. Finally,
383 the overall prediction of the classifier is made according to what has been the most voted class
384 (safe or unsafe) among the 9 decision trees.

Tree 1

Tree 9

k = 9...

385

386 **Figure 5.** 2 of the 9 decision trees that constitute the binary TdP-risk classifier. Each tree takes
387 several decision and makes a prediction. The final output of the classifier is obtained by taking
388 into account the most voted class (safe or unsafe) amongst the 9 decision trees.

389 The performance of this classifier is summarized in the first line of **Table 2**. The accuracy
390 achieved by this classifier is 94.5%, which misclassifies only 6 drugs. The false negatives were
391 donepezil, a class 1 drug, and ritonavir and saquinavir, two class 2 drugs, while the false positives
392 were two class 3 drugs (fluvoxamine and propafenone) and one class 4 compound (cibenzoline).
393 It should be noted that these drugs were also misclassified when using T_x , T_{qNet} and T_{triang}
394 individually as predictors.

395 **Table 2.** Performance of the binary TdP-risk classifier depending on the way of calculating the
396 biomarkers used as input. 4 different classifiers have been built: one considering that drugs affect
397 the 7 CiPA currents; another considering effects on I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} and I_{Ks} ; another assuming effects on
398 I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} and I_{NaL} ; and another combining biomarkers calculated taking into account effects on I_{Kr} ,
399 I_{CaL} and I_{Ks} and biomarker assuming effects on I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} and I_{NaL} . The table indicates the accuracy
400 of the classifier (Acc.), the false negatives and the false positives.

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Currents considered	Acc. (%)	False negatives (% sensitivity)	False positives (% specificity)
I_{Na}, I_{NaL}, I_{to}, I_{Kr}, I_{CaL} I_{Ks} and I_{K1}	94.5	3 (94%) Donepezil Ritonavir Saquinavir	3 (95%) Fluvoxamine Propafenone Cibenzoline
I_{Kr}, I_{CaL} and I_{Ks}	92.7	1 (98%) Cilostazol	7 (88%) Fluvoxamine Propafenone Quinine Ranolazine Cibenzoline Mexiletine Verapamil
I_{Kr}, I_{CaL} and I_{NaL}	93.6	2 (96%) Cilostazol Donepezil	5 (91%) Metronidazole Propafenone Quinine Ranolazine Verapamil
I_{Kr}, I_{CaL}, I_{Ks} and I_{Kr}, I_{CaL}, I_{NaL}	94.5	3 (94%) Cilostazol Donepezil Sotalol	3 (95%) Metronidazole Ranolazine Verapamil

409

410 Based on the sensitivity analysis, we also studied how the proarrhythmic prediction changed
411 when simulating and calculating the biomarkers assuming that drugs affected less currents (the
412 ones with greater impact according to the sensitivity analysis). Thus, biomarkers were recalculated
413 in two different ways: considering that drugs affect only I_{Kr}, I_{CaL}, and I_{Ks}; and considering drugs
414 effects only on I_{Kr}, I_{CaL}, and I_{NaL}. This strategy was adopted because one of the objectives of the
415 work is to provide a ready-to-use tool with the precalculated arrhythmogenic indices implying a
416 big amount of simulations combining blockade of 3 currents (see section 3.5 Precomputed
417 arrhythmogenic indices). Combining the blockade of 4 currents exponentially increases the
418 number of possibilities and simulations to be performed. The performance of the 4 arrhythmogenic
419 biomarkers (including also T_{EAD}) depending on the affected currents considered is shown **Table**

420 **S3.** In general, it can be observed that when considering effects on less currents, the loss of
421 accuracy is very small (less than 2%). In some cases, when simulating the effects on I_{Kr} , I_{NaL} , I_{CaL}
422 the accuracy obtained is the same as when considering effects on the 7 currents. On the other hand,
423 considering that drugs have effects on I_{Kr} , I_{NaL} , and I_{CaL} provides better results than considering
424 I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , and I_{CaL} . This is consistent with the sensitivity analysis, since I_{NaL} has a greater influence
425 than I_{Ks} .

426 With the new biomarker values, two more decision tree-based classifiers were built. In addition,
427 we built a third classifier that combined as input biomarkers calculated in both ways. That means,
428 for example, that two different T_x are considered in the tree, one calculated considering effects on
429 I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{Ks} and another T_x calculated taking into account drugs effects on I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{NaL} .
430 In **Table 2**, we can see how the classification performance changes depending on the currents
431 considered to calculate the biomarkers. As expected, when only the effects on I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{Ks} or
432 on I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{NaL} were considered the accuracy of the classifier decreased, as all the available
433 information was not used. However, this loss of accuracy was remarkably very low. In fact, the
434 accuracy of the classifier that uses biomarkers calculated taking into account drugs effects on I_{Kr} ,
435 I_{CaL} , and I_{NaL} was only 0.9% lower than the accuracy of the classifier that takes into account the 7
436 CiPA currents. The accuracy of the classifier when taking into account effects on I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{Ks}
437 decreased 1.8%. What is more surprising is that when combining biomarkers obtained in both
438 ways (ones considering I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{Ks} , and others considering I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{NaL}), the same level
439 of accuracy that when considering the 7 currents was achieved. In this case the false negatives
440 were the same, while the false positive were two class 3 drugs (fluvoxamine and ranolazine) and
441 one class 4 compound (verapamil).

442 The performance of the classifiers depending on the biomarkers used as inputs is summarized in
443 the **Supplementary Material, Table S4**. It can be observed that the maximum accuracy was
444 obtained when considering the 4 biomarkers (T_x , T_{qNet} , T_{triang} , and T_{EAD}) to build the classifier
445 (95.4%). However, the difference in performance when not considering T_{EAD} in the classifier is
446 that just one more drug was misclassified (94.5% accuracy). In addition, in this case, out of the 3
447 false negatives, only 1 belongs to the class 1 of CredibleMeds (known risk of TdP) while when
448 including T_{EAD} into the classifier, the two false negatives are two class 1 drugs. For this reason,
449 and because T_{EAD} is a complex and computationally expensive biomarker which, as shown in
450 section 3.1, has low predictive power as an individual predictor, T_{EAD} was not included in the
451 preparation of the ready-to-use tool (see section 3.5 for more details). For the other combinations
452 of biomarkers, it can be observed that the accuracy fell slightly. It should also be noted that
453 considering the effect on only 3 currents (I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{NaL} or I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{Ks}) hardly affected the
454 performance of the classifier. Furthermore, when combining biomarkers obtained in both ways
455 (ones considering I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{Ks} , and others considering I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{NaL}), the same level of
456 accuracy that when considering the 7 currents was achieved.

457 3.4. Precomputed arrhythmogenic indices

458 To facilitate the prediction of the potential proarrhythmic risk of a wide range of drugs without
459 carrying out time-consuming simulations, T_x , T_{qNet} , and T_{triang} were precomputed for a large
460 combination of I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , I_{Ks} , and I_{NaL} block values (the most relevant currents according to the
461 sensitivity analysis) and concentration combinations.

462 As mentioned above, combining biomarkers calculated taking into account the effects on I_{Kr} ,
463 I_{CaL} , and I_{Ks} with biomarkers calculated taking into account effects on I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} and I_{NaL} , improves

464 the accuracy of a classifier. Indeed, its performance is very similar to that of the classifier that uses
465 biomarkers calculated assuming effects on the 7 CiPA currents.

466 For this reason, for each of the three biomarkers we constructed two matrices, one in which the
467 biomarker was calculated using a combination of drug concentrations over the IC_{50} of I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and
468 I_{Ks} , and another where the currents blocked were I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{NaL} . Therefore, 492,536 simulations
469 of drug effects on the isolated endocardial myocyte were run with a BCL of 1000 ms, varying the
470 ratios of drug concentration over the IC_{50} of each considered ion channel (I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , and I_{CaL} in one
471 case and I_{Kr} , I_{NaL} , and I_{CaL} in the other case). The logarithm of ratios of drug concentration over
472 the IC_{50} of each considered ion channel (I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , I_{Ks} , and I_{NaL}) ranged from -3 to 1.5, with a 0.1
473 step increment. Note that if we would have tried to calculate the biomarkers for all possible
474 combinations of the 4 currents, the number of simulations would have amounted up to more than
475 8,000,000 simulations. In addition, the representation of the results would have been more
476 complex.

477

478 **Figure 6.** Pre-computed matrices for the following arrhythmogenic indices: T_x (A&B),
 479 T_{qNet} (B&C) and T_{triang} (D&E). As an example of its usage, 4 drugs (2 TdP+ and 2 TdP-) have been
 480 represented in each matrix: ibutilide (red circle), disopyramide (red triangle), loratadine (green
 481 circle) and diltiazem (green triangle). Axis represent the logarithm of the ratio of the drug

482 concentration over the IC_{50} of each channel ($\log([D]/IC_{50})$). (A&B) 3D representation of the
483 surface (blue striped) corresponding to $T_x=8$. Torsadogenic drugs are on the left of this surface and
484 safe drugs stay on the right of the surface. (C&D) 3D representation of the surface (blue striped)
485 corresponding to $T_{qNet}=0.88$. Again, torsadogenic drugs are on the left of this surface. (E&F) 3D
486 representation of the surface (red striped) corresponding to $T_{triang}=1.19$. Torsadogenic drugs are on
487 the left of this surface, where blockades are higher.

488 **Figure 6** shows the 6 matrices calculated. The matrix in Panel A provides the T_x for a given
489 combination of I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{NaL} blockade. The striped surface corresponds to the combination
490 of blockades leading $T_x=8$. Panel B shows T_x matrix depending on I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{Ks} blockade.
491 Panels C and D display the matrices for T_{qNet} . Panels E and F the matrices for T_{triang} . The surfaces
492 represented in each matrix correspond to the optimal cut-off point for each biomarker as an
493 individual predictor ($T_{qNet}=0.88$, $T_{triang}=1.19$, see section 3.1 for more details). These surfaces were
494 represented only as a proof of concept, and different surfaces could have been represented. In each
495 matrix, four drugs have been represented as an example: ibutilide (red circle), disopyramide (red
496 triangle), loratadine (green circle), and diltiazem (green triangle).

497 The matrices can be used with two different purposes. On the one hand, they can be used to
498 quickly predict whether an existing drug, for which all pharmacological data are known, is likely
499 to produce TdP at its EFTPC. On the other hand, in the case of a drug candidate, they may be
500 useful to help determine the TdP risk at a given concentration.

501 As an example, for a prediction based exclusively on T_x , we know that the threshold $T_x = 8$ is
502 the one that best separates TdP+ drugs from TdP-. Therefore, for a well-characterized drug, if we
503 calculate the blockade of I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} , and I_{Ks} (i.e. $\log(EFTPC/IC_{50})$) we can use directly this

504 matrix, without the need to run any simulation, to locate the drug in 3D plots like the ones
505 represented in **Figure 6 (A and B)** to know the associated T_x . We can see that torsadogenic
506 compounds like ibutilide (red circle), disopyramide (red triangle) fall to the right of this surface,
507 meaning that its T_x is lower than 8. Conversely, non-torsadogenic compounds, like loratadine
508 (green circle) and diltiazem (green triangle), fall to the right of the stripped surface. Therefore,
509 their T_x is higher than 8. We can perform a similar approach for the other matrices, based on the
510 cut-off value for each biomarker, so that we can observe that arrhythmogenic drugs are at one side
511 of the surface and safe drugs at the opposite. More accurate predictions can be made using the
512 evaluations of the decision-tree based classifier and combining the different matrices.

513 In the case of new compounds, as the EFTPC is unknown, these matrices can be used to find an
514 estimation of the maximum safe concentration. For this purpose, an initial estimation of the
515 maximum concentration has to be provided instead of the EFTPC, together with the IC_{50} s. For
516 these values, the precomputed matrices will provide a set of indices. They can be compared to the
517 cut-point of each of the decision tree of the classifiers to obtain a set of conditions that must be
518 accomplished in order to classify the drug as a safe compound. Then, if a certain biomarker, like
519 for example T_x , does not accomplish the conditions because it is lower, the concentration should
520 be decreased. On the contrary, if the T_x index is higher than the decision stated by the classifier,
521 that means that the maximum safe concentration could be higher. If instead of T_x , a different index
522 is considered, the procedure would be similar: increase or decrease the concentration to meet the
523 conditions. Thus, to find a maximum safe concentration, the process must be repeated for several
524 concentrations until the biomarkers are as near as possible to the cut-point.

525 Matrices are available on-line on the public repository of the Polytechnic University of Valencia
526 (RIUNET, <https://riunet.upv.es/handle/10251/136919>). Other advantage of these matrices is that

527 by having the value of biomarkers available for a wide variety of drugs, new classification
528 strategies can be proposed.

529 4. DISCUSSION

530 4.1. Main findings

531 In this work, we present a new classifier for the evaluation of drug-induced torsadogenic risk
532 during early stages based on three *in-silico* biomarkers: T_x , T_{qNet} , and T_{triang} . Our main findings
533 are: (i) any of these arrhythmogenic indices, which collect the influence of relevant factors on the
534 development of TdP, perform better than the current preclinical surrogate marker of TdP risk
535 (hERG IC_{50}). (ii) When combining these arrhythmogenic indices into a classifier, the quality of
536 the classification improves, showing better accuracy. The resulting accuracy of the binary
537 classifier is 94.5%, misclassifying only 6 drugs of 109. Misclassifications using the hERG block
538 criterion were 23 (accuracy of 78.9%). It should be noted that our classifiers were developed using
539 109 drugs and effects on 7 ionic currents, being, to our knowledge, one of the largest set of drugs
540 used in arrhythmogenic risk assessment. (iii) Considering drug effects on just 4 currents (I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} ,
541 I_{NaL} , and I_{Ks}), the ones with greater impact on the biomarkers according to the sensitivity analysis,
542 TdP risk classification can be as accurate as when taking into account the blockade of the 7 currents
543 of the CiPA initiative. This may allow experiments to be carried out focusing on those most
544 important currents, accelerating the drug development process and saving significant costs. (iv)
545 Finally, this study also provides a ready-to-use tool available online based on more than 450,000
546 simulations of the electrophysiological activity of ventricular cells. This tool consists of 6 matrices
547 that contain the value of the three biomarkers for a wide range of I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} and I_{Ks} blockades.

548 This allows to quickly assess the cardiotoxicity of existing drugs and helps to predict the maximum
549 safe free plasma concentration of new drugs that prevents TdP appearance.

550 4.2. Arrhythmogenic indices

551 TdP risk-assessment methodologies based exclusively on hERG block show low
552 performance.^{6,10,34} Indeed, when applying the pIC₅₀ hERG test (TdP+: pIC₅₀ hERG >5.8) to the
553 109 compounds studied in this work, the resulting sensitivity was 65% (18 false positives), the
554 specificity was 91% (5 false negatives) and the accuracy was 78.9%. This is in close agreement
555 with previous studies^{10,17,35} proposing classifications based on hERG block that achieved
556 accuracies around 70-80%. In 2003, Redfern et al.³⁶ proposed the ratio of the hERG IC₅₀ over the
557 maximum EFTPC as an improvement over the hERG IC₅₀ index. They observed that a safety factor
558 of 30 could provide a good torsadogenic risk prediction for 52 drugs. This metric has also been
559 used in other studies as a current state-of-the-art measure¹⁶. In this study, in closely agreement
560 with Redfern et al.³⁶, the cut-point obtained for hERG IC₅₀/EFTPC was 39 and also showed better
561 performance than simply hERG IC₅₀. Nevertheless, in comparison, all the *in-silico* biomarkers
562 proposed in this study (with the exception of T_{EAD}) presented a higher performance, reducing the
563 number of misclassified drugs.

564 The classification based on the analysis of EADs, which performed similar to pIC₅₀ hERG, was
565 not as predictive as the other *in-silico* indices. Parikh et al.²⁶ also studied an EAD metric and
566 observed a poor performance compared to other metrics, such as qNet. The reasons for the poor
567 performance of the EAD biomarker might include inaccurate development of EADs in the used
568 ionic model, as EADs are highly dependent on the ventricular cardiomyocyte model, or the need
569 to test EADs on coupled cells/tissue models.²⁶ The influence of the model in the development of

570 EADs can be highlighted in Passini et al.¹³ In their work, they built a population of models by
571 modifying some conductances of the O'Hara model within a physiological range. This way, they
572 could cover a wider biological variability than just with a single AP and thus EADs obtained good
573 accuracy as a biomarker for TdP risk. Another problem related to O'Hara's model, which can
574 explain the poor performance of EADs as a biomarker, is that it does not reproduce well the
575 negative inotropic effect observed experimentally when simultaneously blocking I_{Na} and I_{NaL} .
576 Recently, Tomek et al.³⁷ published a model aiming to better reproduce this inotropic effect. Using
577 Tomek et al. model or other action potential models will obviously result in different performance
578 of EAD as biomarker (and also the performance of the others biomarkers), but this does not reduce
579 the validity of the results presented in this work.

580 In a previous work¹⁰, we showed that the prediction of TdP risk could be improved with the T_x
581 index. In that study, T_x was calculated taking into account the effects of drugs on I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , and I_{CaL}
582 and when applied to 84 compounds it exhibited an accuracy of 87%. Here, considering drug effects
583 on four currents to calculate T_x and applying this test to more drugs (109 drugs), the resulting
584 accuracy was 89.9%. The threshold was the same in both works ($T_x < 8$ for TdP+ compounds).
585 Therefore, this demonstrates that T_x is a robust and effective biomarker that can successfully be
586 used for TdP-risk evaluation.

587 As in previous recent studies^{5,15,26}, T_{qNet} provided the most accurate proarrhythmic prediction
588 among the 4 biomarkers. It should be said that Dutta et al.¹⁵ correctly classified 100% using qNet
589 metric, but the dataset studied was composed only by the 12 CiPA training drugs. Here, when
590 evaluating it with a larger set of drugs, its performance decreases. This is in accordance with Li et
591 al.⁵ results, where it is shown that qNet performance also decreases when considering the total 28
592 CiPA compounds. Note that T_{qNet} and qNet at 10xEFTPC perform equally, as T_{qNet} is qNet divided

593 by a constant (q_{Net} at control conditions). The advantage of using $T_{q_{\text{Net}}}$ is that it is a relative
594 measure, which makes it independent of the model used. We chose 10xEFTPC because it is a
595 concentration that produces significant drug effects without being an excessively high
596 concentration. T_{triang} is also a relative metric that quantifies changes with respect to control
597 conditions, which is an advantage with respect triangulation. To our knowledge, T_{triang} has not been
598 used previously as an *in-silico* classifier, however, it shows a performance very similar to that of
599 previous TdP-risk classification works. Mirams et al.⁸ assessed the performance of the prediction
600 of the thorough QT assay in 34 drugs obtaining 88% accuracy, 71% sensitivity, and 100%
601 specificity. Lancaster and Sobie¹² have also evaluated arrhythmia risk combining multichannel
602 block simulation of 68 drugs with statistical analysis and machine-learning techniques achieving
603 89.5% accuracy, 95.9% sensitivity, and 81.1% specificity. Kramer et al.¹⁷ observed that the TdP
604 risk prediction provided by the comparison of the blocking potencies between I_{Kr} and I_{CaL} was
605 drastically better than the prediction obtained by the hERG assay in 55 drugs (90.9% accuracy,
606 96.9% sensitivity, and 86.2% specificity). Parikh et al.²⁴ proposed a novel classifier that combined
607 direct features (IC_{60} hERG) and 13 derived features. It provided an accuracy of 83% when tested
608 in merged dataset of 197 drugs (some drugs were repeated as they were simulated using different
609 drug models). Passini et al.³⁸ achieved an accuracy of 90% evaluating TdP risk of 40 drugs by
610 measuring the shortening of the electromechanical window and repolarizations abnormalities. Li
611 et al.⁵ showed that the metric *torsade metric score*, which is the q_{Net} value averaged across 1-4 x
612 C_{max} taking into account drug effects on the currents I_{Kr} , I_{Na} , I_{NaL} and I_{CaL} , could successfully
613 predict the TdP risk of the 16 CiPA compounds, outperforming other *in-silico* metrics such as
614 APD90 or APD50 plus diastolic Ca^{2+} concentration. Recently, Zhou et al.³⁹ used the TdP risk
615 score, a metric which summarizes repolarization abnormalities among a population of

616 cardiomyocytes, to study how different prediction outcomes were, depending on the input data
617 (IC_{50} and Hill coefficient). This metric demonstrated good performance, showing an accuracy
618 superior than 80% on two different drugs datasets.

619 In addition, we showed that combining T_x , T_{qNet} , and T_{triang} in a binary classifier based on
620 decision trees improves the accuracy of risk classification up to 94.5%. In addition, this level of
621 performance can be achieved simulating effects only on I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} , and I_{Ks} , which are the
622 currents with greater impact on the arrhythmogenic indices according to the sensitivity analysis.
623 These results are comparable or even better than other more complex systems that perform 3D
624 simulations, and to *in-vitro* experiments with cells or whole hearts. Okada et al.¹⁴ simulated a total
625 of 9075 electrocardiograms using a 3D whole-ventricle model for a combination of blocks of I_{Kr} ,
626 I_{Na} , I_{NaL} , I_{CaL} , and I_{Ks} . Using this system, they evaluated 13 drugs, successfully classifying 92%.
627 Lawrence et al.⁴⁰ used the rabbit isolated Langerdorff heart model to investigate the torsadogenic
628 risk of 64 compounds with an accuracy of 75%. Ando et al.⁴¹ recorded extracellular field potentials
629 from human iPSC-derived cardiomyocytes to evaluate 60 drugs achieving a sensitivity of 81%,
630 specificity of 87%, and accuracy of 83%.

631 We observed that there was a group of drugs that was misclassified in all or in almost all cases.
632 This indicates that the model is not reproducing correctly some drug effects or that experimental
633 data might have some bias. There are pharmacological aspects that were not considered in this
634 study mainly due to lack of information, such as effects of metabolites, accumulation of the
635 compound in the myocardium, channel trafficking inhibition, among others (all of them not
636 included in the electrophysiological model used). It has been demonstrated that donepezil
637 increased TdP incidence not only by I_{Kr} block but also by I_{Kr} trafficking inhibition^{42,43}. Ritonavir
638 and saquinavir, which are misclassified with the binary classifier, are known to inhibit major

639 isoforms of cytochrome P450¹⁴ which metabolize many drugs, including torsadogenic drugs such
640 bepridil or quinidine. Thus, rather than its arrhythmogenic capacity per se, its torsadogenicity is
641 due to the increase in the amount of other dangerous drugs. Cilostazol inhibits phosphodiesterase
642 3 (PDE3), which causes an increase of intracellular cAMP, Ca²⁺ dynamic unbalance, and
643 precipitation of EADs⁴⁴. Fluvoxamine has been classified as a class 3 compound by CredibleMeds,
644 so here it was considered as TdP-. However, some clinical studies^{45,46} reported that fluvoxamine,
645 at therapeutic doses, increases the risk of TdP induction. These authors recommend that patients
646 on fluvoxamine treatment should be monitored closely for QT/QTc interval prolongation with
647 serial ECG. For propafenone something similar occurred: it was classified as a class 3 compound
648 by CredibleMeds but different studies^{47,48} alert about its TdP-risk. In addition, in the American
649 College of Cardiology website there is a black box warning stating: “potentially fatal ventricular
650 arrhythmias may occur with/without QT prolongation and can lead to torsade de pointes”. It is
651 worth noting that for cibenzoline only two works reporting an IC₅₀ I_{Kr} value were found and the
652 difference between these two values was more than an order of magnitude. Therefore, its effect on
653 I_{Kr} might have been overestimated and therefore resulted in a false positive. In the case of
654 verapamil, the reason of its misclassification could be an overestimation of IC₅₀ I_{Kr} that produces
655 such a blockade that cannot be counteracted by I_{CaL} blockade to avoid prolongation of the action
656 potential¹⁹. Therefore, it seems that this mechanism would require fine tuning of the I_{CaL} and I_{Kr}
657 ratios.

658 Other authors have predicted cardiac safety of torsadogenic drugs simulating drug effects in
659 isolated endocardial cells of different species such as guinea pigs⁹, dogs or rabbits. Beattie et al.⁴⁹
660 predicted the experimental results of the rabbit left ventricular wedge assay using *in-silico*
661 simulations of the QT prolongation of the rabbit left ventricular wedge assay (78% accuracy). We

662 chose a modified version of the O'Hara et al.¹⁸ human ventricular AP model for our simulations
663 instead of models of other species in order to obtain more accurate predictions of drug effects in
664 humans⁵⁰. In fact, compared to human cardiomyocytes, guinea pig cardiomyocytes showed a lack
665 of transient outward current (I_{to}) and a large I_{Ks} , and rabbit cardiomyocytes presented a small slow
666 delayed rectifier current (I_{Ks}) and TdP predisposition.⁵¹ In the human ventricular AP model we
667 decided not to introduce the dynamic-hERG model⁵², which is the most updated version
668 recommended by CiPA initiative for prediction of TdP, because many drugs do not have the
669 experimental data necessary to model their effect and significantly increases the computational
670 cost without providing significant benefits for the simulation of the effects of many drugs.¹⁹

671 4.3. Sensitivity analysis

672 Our sensitivity analysis of the virtual population of drugs identified critical ionic currents for the
673 variability of the different arrhythmogenic biomarkers studied for TdP risk assessment. The
674 sensitivity analysis was performed using three different methods (see section 2.4) and the three
675 methods identify the same currents as the most influential: I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} , and I_{Ks} .

676 In agreement with previous studies^{8,18,20,23,26,53}, I_{Kr} inhibition and I_{NaL} and I_{CaL} enhancement
677 prolong APD_{90} and increase triangulation. Parikh et al.²⁶ also obtained that T_{qNet_mod} was more
678 sensitive to changes in I_{NaL} and I_{Kr} . This relevant role of I_{NaL} is in agreement with experimental
679 results indicating drug-induced enhancement of I_{NaL} can result in increased TdP risk in the absence
680 of hERG block.^{54,55} Furthermore, accordingly to Parikh et al.²⁶, we have seen that some ion
681 channels that are thought to be important for drug-induced TdP risk assessment and measured
682 experimentally via *in-vitro* ion-channel screening⁵⁶ showed minor influence on the
683 arrhythmogenic biomarkers. For example, the block of I_{to} had no influence on most of the metrics.

684 These facts suggest that the experimental and *in-silico* study of the effects of drugs on I_{Kr} , I_{NaL} ,
685 I_{CaL} , and I_{Ks} is more relevant than drug effects on I_{to} , I_{Na} or I_{K1} for the assessment of TdP risk.
686 Uncertainties in the input parameters that are highly influential, such as pharmacological data of
687 the effects on hERG channel, result in lower confidence in the predicted TdP risk, while errors in
688 estimating less influential model parameters are better tolerated by risk measurements. Thus,
689 Costabal et al.⁵³ showed that the variability in I_{Kr} block, the current with greatest sensitivity here,
690 was primarily responsible for the uncertainty of QT interval simulations. In this work, we have
691 demonstrated that using data from I_{Kr} , I_{NaL} , I_{CaL} , and I_{Ks} , torsadogenicity prediction is very similar
692 to the results obtained using the 7 currents. Recently, Zhou et al.³⁹ claimed that the minimum set
693 of ion channels needed to correctly assess TdP risk were I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} and I_{Na} . One of the reasons that
694 explain this discrepancy between the minimum set of currents may be that they only compared the
695 prediction results when considering drug effects on the 7 currents, 4 (I_{Na} , I_{NaL} , I_{Kr} and I_{CaL}), 3 (I_{Na} ,
696 I_{Kr} and I_{CaL}), or 1 (I_{Kr}). Perhaps if other combinations of currents had been tested, other set of
697 currents would have also led to similar accuracy. In addition, experimental data on I_{NaL} IC_{50} are
698 only available for 25 of the 85 drugs studied. There are also very few data available for IC_{50} I_{Ks} .
699 However, their results agree with the current study in the fact that not all 7 CiPA currents are
700 necessary. Simulating drug effects on a lower number of currents can achieve very accurate
701 predictions. Furthermore, in both studies I_{Kr} and I_{CaL} are a fundamental requirement. Our study
702 suggest that they should be complemented with I_{NaL} or I_{Ks} to improve the accuracy of the
703 prediction.

704 4.4. Limitations of the study

705 One of the strengths of this work is the use of a large drug dataset including information of 7
706 ionic currents. However, the IC_{50} values of some ionic currents of certain drugs were absent in the

707 literature or public repositories. For example, to our knowledge, the only work that provides
708 information about I_{NaL} block potency is Crumb et al.⁵⁶, and they only studied 30 compounds. As
709 illustrated above, I_{NaL} is one of the most influential currents in TdP prediction, so having more
710 information about the blocking of I_{NaL} could improve the performance of the classifiers proposed
711 here. For I_{to} and I_{K1} available IC_{50} data were also scarce. In these cases, similarly to previous
712 works^{8,10,24}, no block of these channels was assumed. In addition, the IC_{50} and EFTPC values were
713 consulted in heterogeneous sources, which suggests that the experimental conditions were very
714 diverse and therefore there is also great variability in the collected data. In fact, some authors⁵⁷
715 have found that the IC_{50} values of I_{Kr} can vary by one or two orders of magnitude between different
716 studies. Due to lack of a standard protocols, dealing with multiple IC_{50} for a given compound is a
717 challenging task which can be addressed in different ways. We reduced sources of variability by
718 obtaining data from mammalian tissue registers when available and always avoiding data extracted
719 from *Xenopus* oocytes. In addition, when multiple IC_{50} values were available for a given drug, the
720 median value was calculated. As recently demonstrated by Zhou et al.³⁹, for compounds with
721 multiple ion channel potencies, variations in IC_{50} value can lead to different *in-silico* predictions.
722 In this work, they studied prediction divergencies using two different datasets: Crumb's dataset⁵⁶
723 and Kramer's dataset¹⁷. They showed that the accuracy when using Crumb's values was slightly
724 higher than when using Kramer's values. Here, we considered that the published data represented
725 a distribution of values affected by a random error plus the variability due to the experimental
726 conditions. Then, the most representative value considering variability was the median as it is a
727 robust estimator of the central tendency of a data set, less sensitive to extreme values than the
728 average. Further studies on uncertainty quantification will help to better understand model's
729 tolerability of input variability. In addition, standardization of experimental protocols, with well-

730 defined environmental conditions, could help increase the model prediction accuracy, as it has
731 been highlighted by Li et al.⁵ Recently, Gomis-Tena et al.⁵⁸ showed that for some drugs, even
732 maintaining the same experimental conditions, IC₅₀ value may vary depending on the voltage
733 clamp protocol used and propose the adoption of a three-protocol IC₅₀ assay to measure the
734 potency to block hERG.

735 Here, similarly to others studies⁵, we used the cross validation method to validate TdP-risk
736 predictions, where for each iteration some drugs are used as training set and others as validation
737 set. Recently, Li et al.⁵⁹ proposed a new training-validation strategy to validate TdP prediction
738 models. They proposed that the models should be validated by an external set of drugs (“hidden”
739 validation group), where experimental data are not even collected for validation drugs during the
740 model training stage. In this sense, this strategy could be taken into account in the future.

741 On the other hand, we simulated drug effects using the simple pore block model, which assumes
742 that the union between drug and channel can occur in any channel conformation and that the
743 channel activity kinetics remain unchanged after binding⁶⁰. This may be too simplistic and may
744 not capture adequately complex pharmacokinetic or pharmacodynamic effects. For example, drug
745 binding kinetics, which were not considered in this work, have been related to increased
746 susceptibility to acquired long QT syndrome in the presence of hERG channel kinetic
747 abnormalities.⁵² Simulation of hERG drug binding kinetics could have been modeled through the
748 recently introduced dynamic-hERG model^{61,62}. However, experimental parameters needed to
749 simulate drug effects are scarce because they are measured using complex experimental
750 protocols.²⁴ This dynamic-hERG model needs 5 more parameters to simulate the effects of a given
751 drug, and it has been proved that parameters such as V_{half} and K_u contribute relatively little to the

752 variation of q_{Net} , APD_{90} and $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ peak¹⁹. In addition, using these models does not bring benefits
753 for many drugs as there are no significant changes in the simulations⁶³.

754 Our simulations do not consider other pharmacological aspects such as drug-drug interactions,
755 effects of active metabolites, accumulation of drugs in cardiac tissue, effects on autonomic nervous
756 system, protein binding alterations, etc. Drug-drug interactions play a role in torsadogenic
757 induction of drugs such as clozapine and risperidone⁶⁴ or domperidone⁶⁵. The incorporation of
758 such aspects, could have enriched the results of this study. Unfortunately, further experimental
759 studies are needed to provide the data for all the compounds considered here to allow the
760 simulation of these phenomena. Nevertheless, it can be said that the levels of accuracy obtained in
761 this work suggest that the most relevant biophysical processes contributing to the induction of TdP
762 have been correctly represented.

763 Other limitation of this work is that the results of the classification depend largely on the
764 information taken as reference. Here, drugs were classified according to CredibleMeds database,
765 which feeds from clinical data and is well-recognized by the scientific community. We have
766 considered class 3 (conditional risk drugs) as TdP-, since we have focused on the individual
767 pharmacological effects (not interactions) on healthy cells and therefore we considered that these
768 special conditions did not take place and these drugs had little probability of causing TdP. In
769 addition, we have considered the worst possible scenario, that is, the highest EFTPC of those
770 published. However, specific conditions such as overdose can increase arrhythmogenic potential
771 of these drugs. In this sense, we tested how the prediction of the TdP-risk classifier for class 3
772 compound changed under therapeutic doses or under overdose conditions (10xEFTPC). As
773 previously shown (**Table 2**), at 1xEFTPC there is just one class 3 drug (fluvoxamine) that is
774 predicted by the decision tree-based classifier as TdP+; while in overdose conditions, 7 out of these

775 13 drugs increased its torsadogenicity and were considered as TdP+: fluvoxamine plus
776 diphenhydramine, metronidazole, paroxetine, quetiapine, solifenacin and voriconazole.
777 Furthermore, some other drugs may change their level of proarrythmicity depending on the
778 database. For example, drugs such as astemizole, chlorpromazine, cisapride, clarithromycin,
779 domperidone, droperidol, terfenadine, pimozone or ondansetron which are considered as high-risk
780 drugs according to CredibleMeds, belong to the group of intermediate risk drugs in the CiPA
781 developing set. Ranolazine and tamoxifen are intermediate risk drugs according to CredibleMeds,
782 but they are low risk according to the CiPA set. In fact, Wisniowska and Polak⁶⁵ provided a large
783 number of drugs with contradicting classification amongst different databases. Thus, different
784 categorizations can lead to different accuracy and performance of the TdP risk classifier. This
785 highlights the need of a standardized TdP-risk drug classification to obtain a wide database (ground
786 truth) that helps researchers to develop new tools for proarrhythmic risk prediction.

787 5. CONCLUSIONS

788 In this work, we describe a new *in-silico* tool to study effects of a drug on the
789 electrophysiological properties of a cardiomyocyte and thus predict its proarrhythmic risk. Our
790 results highlight that *in-silico* simulations considering the EFTPC and the effects on ionic currents
791 improves the prediction of cardiotoxicity – in addition to well-proven influence of hERG IC₅₀
792 (current TdP risk biomarker according to S7B ICH guideline) on likelihood of TdP. We also show
793 that it is not necessary to simulate the drug effects on the main 7 ionic currents proposed by CiPA
794 to have a good prediction of the proarrhythmicity of a compound. With experimental data of 4
795 currents (I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , I_{NaL} and I_{Ks} , which are the currents with greater impact on the arrhythmogenic
796 indices according to the sensitivity analysis), TdP prediction can be significantly accurate. In
797 addition, we provide a ready-to-use tool which can be used to estimate the maximum safe free

798 plasma concentration in the different phases of drug discovery or to quickly assess the
799 proarrhythmicity of a drug with known EFTPC and IC₅₀s. We believe that the usage of such *in-*
800 *silico* tools as screening methods could be helpful to accelerate the development of new drugs and
801 reducing costs of the cardiac safety screening in preclinical phases. In addition, this approach has
802 the potential to lead to a major replacement of animal experiments in the early stages of drug
803 development.

804 **Supporting Information.**

805 The following files are available free of charge.

806 Supporting Information (PDF). It contains:

807 **Table S1.** Equations of the activation (m_{ss}) and inactivation gates (h_{ss} , h_{ssp} and j_{ss})
808 at the steady state of the rapid Na⁺ current in the O'Hara et al. model and in the
809 modified version.

810 **Table S2.** IC₅₀ values (nM), Hill coefficients and effective free therapeutic plasma
811 concentration (EFTPC) (nM) used to simulated the 109 drugs studied in this work.

812 **Table S3.** Performance of the 4 arrhythmogenic biomarkers depending on the
813 currents on which the effect of the drug is assumed: the 7 CiPA currents; I_{Kr}, I_{CaL}
814 and I_{Ks}, or, I_{Kr}, I_{CaL} and I_{NaL}.

815 **Table S4.** Performance of the classifiers depending on the biomarkers used as
816 inputs.

817 **Figure S1.** Results of the sensitivity analysis with the multiple linear regression
818 method.

819 **Figure S2.** Results of the sensitivity analysis applying the PLS method.

820 **Figure S3.** Decision trees that constitute the binary TdP-risk classifier based on T_x ,

821 T_{qNet} and T_{triang}

822 T_x , T_{qNet} and T_{triang} pre-computed matrices and Matlab functions used in this work are
823 available free of charge at: <https://riunet.upv.es/handle/10251/136919>.

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828 **Author Contributions**

829 JL contributed to the design of the study, performed the simulations, analyzed results and wrote
830 the first draft of the manuscript. JG implemented the model in C++, built the matrices of the
831 precomputed indices and obtained the figures of the matrices. BT and JS contributed to the design
832 of the study, analyzed the results and supervised the project. All authors contributed to manuscript
833 revision, read and approved the submitted version.

834 **Notes**

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